

Studies on the Formation of Azoxy, Azo, Hydrazo and Benzidine Compounds and the Dyes Derived from the Latter.

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In the present work, the action of zinc dust and caustic soda, and zinc dust and ammonium chloride on aromatic nitro compounds has been further investigated with a view to study (a) the influence of the nature and position of the substituents on the formation of the azoxy, azo and hydrazo compounds and also on the subsequent benzidine transformation, and (b) the tinctorial properties of the dyes derived from the resulting benzidine compounds.

Reduction with caustic soda and zinc dust is now found to be very efficacious in the preparation of azo and hydrazo compounds from substituted nitrobenzenes *viz.*, *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, *m*- and *o*-nitrophenols, *m*- and *o*-nitrobenzaldehydes (*cf.* Loewenherz, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2795). In the case of the nitroaldehydes not only is the nitro group reduced, but the aldehydo group also undergoes reduction to the primary alcoholic group.

Comparing the yields obtained and the time of reduction of the nitro compounds to the hydrazo stage, it is found that the *meta* substituent influences the reduction more favourably than the *ortho*, although substitution in general retards the reduction of the nitro group. It is observed that the aldehydo group exerts the most and the phenolic group the least favourable influence on the formation of the hydrazo compounds.

The mixture of zinc and ammonium chloride, previously used by Cumming and Steel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2464) for the reduction of α -nitronaphthalene to hydrazo and azo compounds, is found to be not suitable for the reduction of ordinary aromatic nitro compounds, although a heterocyclic nitro compound such as 6-nitrocoumarin is readily reduced yielding 60 per cent. azoxycoumarin and 30 per cent. aminocoumarin. 6-Nitrocoumarin is however completely reduced to

6-aminocoumarin by the action of zinc dust and caustic soda. Azoxycoumarin is very similar in properties to the azocoumarin synthesised by coupling diazotised 6-aminocoumarin with coumarin (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 506). The solution of the compound in caustic soda undergoes geometrical inversion with mercuric oxide (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247; Chakravarti, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 391). It is remarkable that azoxycoumarin on further reduction is converted wholly into aminocoumarin, no azo and hydrazo compounds being produced.

On the benzidine transformation of the hydrazo compounds studied, the position and the nature of the substituents appear to have a marked influence. It is found from the yield of benzidine derivatives from the hydrazo compounds investigated that of the groups OH, COOH, and CH₂OH, the OH group is most favourable for benzidine transformation while the CH₂OH group retards it. It is also observed that generally the *meta* substituent is more favourable for the benzidine transformation than the *ortho* substituent excepting the alcoholic group which when in the *meta* position does not exert any beneficial influence.

The new substituted benzidine compounds, prepared and described in this paper have also been tetrazotised, and the azo-dyes obtained from them by coupling with β -naphthol and β -naphthol sulphonic acid are substantive to cotton, while those obtained by coupling with dimethylaniline and β -naphthylamine behave like ordinary basic dyes. It is found that in all cases the azo-dyes derived from the *ortho* substituted derivatives produce deeper shades than the corresponding *meta* compounds. It is remarkable that even the *meta* compounds yield dyestuffs substantive to cotton which is not generally the case.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For the reduction of the nitro compounds to azo and hydrazo compounds with zinc dust, the mixture was mechanically stirred throughout the reaction. The stirrer passed through the inner tube of the condenser fitted to the flask containing the alcoholic solution of the nitro compound and zinc dust, caustic soda solution being added drop by drop from the top of the condenser. In the case of nitrocoumarin the zinc dust was slowly added through a second tube in the cork fitted to the flask, which was closed after each addition.

6-Azoxycoumarin.—6-Nitrocoumarin purified by crystallising from hot pyridine (10 g.) was mixed with alcohol (80 c.c.), ammonium

chloride (21 g.) and water (25 c.c.) added. Zinc dust (18 g.) was gradually added keeping the temperature between, 70-75°. In about 45 minutes the reaction was over. After cooling, the precipitated azoxycoumarin along with the zinc dust was filtered and washed repeatedly with boiling water to remove traces of aminocoumarin formed, which crystallised out from the filtrate. The mixture of the azoxycoumarin and zinc dust was treated in small quantities with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the zinc dust. It crystallised from hot nitrobenzene as pale yellow clusters of thin long needles melting above 300°, yield 60 p.c. It is insoluble in most organic solvents except hot pyridine and nitrobenzene. It is soluble in caustic soda solution with a deep orange colour, but is insoluble in ammonia, sodium carbonate or bicarbonate solutions. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour and is reprecipitated on dilution. (Found: N, 8.29. $C_{18}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent.).

Azoxy-o-coumaric Acid.

Azoxycoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in a 10 p. c. solution of caustic soda (20 c.c.) diluted with water (180 c.c.) and boiled for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with mercuric oxide (3 g.). The cold solution was filtered from mercuric oxide and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The gelatinous precipitate, thus obtained was washed with water, dissolved in ammonia, filtered and filtrate acidified, with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was crystallised from alcohol as a yellow microcrystalline powder decomposing above 270°. It decolorises bromine water and dilute potassium permanganate solution readily in the cold. It easily dissolves in alcohol, acetone, dilute ammonia, sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions. With concentrated hydrochloric acid its colour changes to deep violet. (Found: N, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.73 per cent.).

The *diethyl ester*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol as a brownish yellow powder melting above 250°, yield 70 p. c. (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_2$ requires N, 6.56 per cent.).

m-Hydrazobenzoic acid.—To a mechanically stirred mixture of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (9 g.) zinc dust (24 g.) and alcohol (20 c.c.), a solution of caustic soda (12 g.) in water (40 c.c.) was added drop by

drop in about 1 hour, keeping the temperature at about 90°. When the solution became colourless, it was filtered and the alcohol distilled off in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The solution was then filtered and treated with excess of dilute acetic acid and the precipitated *m*-hydrazobenzoic acid washed and dried, yield about 65 p.c. It was found identical with the compound obtained by Greiss (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1609) and by Strecker (*Annalen*, 1867, 141, 129) by different methods. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10·29 per cent.).

m-Diaminodiphenic acid.—The reduced alkaline solution containing the *m*-hydrazobenzoic acid was freed from zinc and boiled with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid for a short time and left overnight. The precipitated dihydrochloride of *m*-diaminodiphenic acid was crystallised from hot water in white prisms from which the base itself was obtained as a microcrystalline solid by boiling with sodium acetate solution. It is easily soluble in caustic soda solution, sparingly in water and almost insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10·29 per cent.).

m-Dihydroxybenzidine.—This compound was obtained by reducing *m*-nitrophenol and subsequent benzidine transformation of the hydrazo compound thus formed in a similar way to the above. It crystallised from acetone in plates, m.p. 140°, and was found to be identical with the compound obtained by Elbs and Kirsch from *m*-azophenol (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, ii, 67, 265). (Found: N, 12·84. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12·96 per cent.).

o-Hydrazophenol.—An alcoholic solution of *o*-nitrophenol was reduced as previously described with zinc dust and caustic soda until colourless. The solution was freed from zinc, the alcohol distilled off in an atmosphere of hydrogen, and the residue exactly neutralised with dilute acetic acid at 5°. The hydrazophenol that was precipitated along with zinc hydroxide was extracted with ether and the ether evaporated off in vacuum. It crystallised in colourless plates, m.p. 148°, yield 55 p.c. (approx.). It is soluble in hot water, alcohol, ether, dilute hydrochloric acid and dilute caustic soda solutions. It darkens on exposure and it gives a deep red coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 12·8. $O_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12·96 per cent.).

Dibenzoyl derivative crystallised from chloroform as a brownish red microcrystalline powder, m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 6·47. $C_{26}H_{12}O_2N_4$ requires N, 6·6 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxybenzidine was prepared easily by directly treating the reduced solution after filtering off the zinc, with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid at 0° and boiling the solution for a short time. On keeping overnight, the dihydrochloride crystallised as colourless plates. The free base was completely precipitated from aqueous hydrochloride solution with sodium carbonate. It crystallised from acetone in plates, m.p. 160°, yield 30 p.c. Hot water solution gives red precipitate with ferric chloride. It is soluble in dilute acids, caustic soda and sodium carbonate solutions, alcohol and acetone. (Found: N, 12·92. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12·96 per cent.).

The dihydrochloride crystallised in colourless plates, m.p. 144°. (Found: Cl, 24·7. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24·5 per cent.).

Tetrazobenzoyl derivative crystallised from chloroform as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 4·24. $C_{40}H_{28}O_6N_2$ requires N, 4·4 per cent.).

Dibromo derivative was prepared by adding bromine water to a solution of *o*-dihydroxybenzidine in dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from alcohol as a red microcrystalline powder, m.p. 174°. (Found: Br, 42·66. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 42·78 per cent.).

Bismethylbenzoxazole was prepared by boiling *o*-dihydroxybenzidine with excess of acetic acid and fused sodium acetate for about 2 hours. The product was washed with acetic acid and crystallised from alcohol as glistening plates, m.p. 137°. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires, N, 10·6 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxybenzidinebisazo- β -naphthol.—A solution of *o*-dihydroxybenzidine was tetrazotised and coupled with an alkaline solution of β -naphthol, after keeping overnight the precipitated sodium salt was filtered and dried. It is a violet powder soluble in water and dyes cotton and wool to a pink shade. (Found: Na, 13·02. $C_{32}H_{20}O_4N_4Na_2$ requires Na, 13·26 per cent.).

It crystallised from alcohol as a reddish brown microcrystalline powder, m.p. 150°. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{32}H_{22}O_4N_4$ requires N, 10·8 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxybenzidinebisazo- β -naphthol sulphonic acid (2:6).—Tetrazotised *o*-dihydroxybenzidine was coupled with a faintly alkaline solution of β -naphthol sulphonic acid. The reddish brown powder obtained on acidification, decomposes above 250° and dyes cotton and silk a pinkish shade. (Found: N, 8·12. $C_{32}H_{22}O_{10}N_4S_2$ requires N, 8·26 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxybenzidinebisazo- β -naphthylamine.—Tetrazotised *o*-dihydroxybenzidine was coupled with a solution of β -naphthylamine in acetic acid and the dye was precipitated with sodium acetate as an orange powder melting above 250°. It gives a deep orange solution in acetic acid. (Found: N, 16.12. $C_{32}H_{26}O_4N_6$ requires N, 15.96 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxybenzidinebisazodimethylaniline was prepared by coupling tetrazotised dihydroxybenzidine with dimethylaniline in glacial acetic acid. It was purified from alcohol, m.p. above 250°. (Found: N, 19.81. $C_{28}H_{32}O_2N_6$ requires N, 20.0 per cent.).

m-Azobenzyl alcohol.—A solution of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (10 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) was reduced at about 90° using zinc dust (18 g.) and a solution of caustic soda (14 g. in water 40 c.c.). In about 40 minutes the solution attained a very deep red colour, when the reduction was stopped and the alcohol distilled off. On cooling *m*-azobenzyl alcohol crystallised out. It recrystallised from hot water in orange yellow needles, m. p. 117°. It is freely soluble in alcohol and acetone and insoluble in benzene and ether. (Found: N, 11.44. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.57 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone as a yellow microcrystalline powder. (Found: N, 7.2. $C_{28}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.05 per cent.).

m-Hydrazobenzyl alcohol.—*m*-Nitrobenzaldehyde was reduced as in the previous case until colourless. The hydrazo compound crystallised from pyridine, as a yellow microcrystalline powder, m. p. 268°, yield 75 p. c. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol but easily dissolves in sodium carbonate and caustic soda solutions. (Found: N, 11.4. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.51 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as yellow microcrystalline powder decomposing above 220°. (Found: N, 8.34. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.56 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative crystallised from chloroform as a crystalline yellow solid. (Found: N, 6.79. $C_{28}C_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.93 per cent.).

m-Dihydroxymethylbenzidine.—The reduced alkaline solution of above containing the hydrazobenzyl alcohol was freed from zinc and boiled with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid for about 20 minutes; after 3 or 4 hours the solution was filtered and neutralised by the gradual addition of sodium hydroxide solution, when the *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine separated as a pale yellow precipitate.

The base was recrystallised from acetone as a white powder, m. p. 177°, yield 28 p. c. It is easily soluble in dilute acids and dilute caustic soda solution. (Found: N, 11·8. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11·51 per cent.).

Tetrabenzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as microcrystalline powder, m. p. 293°. (Found: N, 8·13. $C_{42}H_{32}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8·28 per cent.).

Tetracetyl derivative, prepared by the usual method crystallised from alcohol as brown microcrystalline plate melting above 250°. (Found: N, 6·83. $C_{22}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6·9 per cent.).

Dibromo derivative, prepared by adding bromine water to a solution of *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine in dilute hydrochloric acid, crystallised from alcohol as a deep brownish red microcrystalline powder melting above 270°. (Found: Br, 41·5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 41·8 per cent.).

m-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol*.—*m*-Dihydroxymethylbenzidine (2 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with an alkaline solution of *β*-naphthol (2·95 g.). The azo-dye was purified from alcohol as a deep orange powder. It dyes silk a deep red shade from acetic acid bath. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{34}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires N, 10·1 per cent.).

m-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol sulphonic acid* (2:6) was prepared from tetrazotised *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine and *β*-naphthol sulphonic acid in the usual manner. It is a reddish brown powder which decomposes on heating. The aqueous solution dyes cotton and silk a deep red shade. (Found: N, 7·8. $C_{34}H_{24}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 7·7 per cent.).

m-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthylamine* was prepared from *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine and purified from alcohol as an orange red powder, m. p. 120°. (Found: N, 14·1. $C_{34}H_{28}O_2N_6$ requires N, 14·4 per cent.).

m-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazodimethylaniline*, prepared from *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine and dimethylaniline, crystallised from alcohol as an orange microcrystalline powder, m. p. above 250°. It dissolves in acetic acid to a deep purple solution from which it dyes silk to a light orange shade. (Found: N, 16·57. $C_{30}H_{32}O_2N_6$ requires N, 16·5 per cent.).

o-*Hydrazobenzyl alcohol*.—The method adopted was the same as that in the case of *m*-hydrazobenzyl alcohol using *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde instead. The hydrazo stage was reached after 3 hours and the hydrazobenzyl alcohol crystallised from pyridine as a white microcrystalline powder.

talline powder, m. p. 200°, yield 70 p.c. It is easily soluble in sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide solutions but is almost insoluble in alcohol or acetone. On boiling it with concentrated hydrochloric acid it is converted after about 10 minutes to *o*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine. (Found: N, 11.4. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.5 per cent.).

Diacetyl derivative crystallised from hot glacial acetic acid as soft needles, m.p. above 250°. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.5c per cent.).

Dibenzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as a pale brown microcrystalline powder, m.p. 107°. (Found: N, 6.86. $C_{26}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.93 per cent.).

o-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidine*.—The procedure adopted was the same as in the case of the preparation of *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine but starting with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde instead. It crystallised from acetone as a red microcrystalline powder, m.p. 185°, yield 40 p. c. It is soluble in alcohol, dilute acids and dilute caustic soda solution. (Found: N, 11.65. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.5 per cent.).

Tetrabenzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. above 250°. It is sparingly soluble in chloroform and insoluble in benzene. (Found: N, 3.1. $C_{42}H_{32}O_6N_2$ requires N, 3.23 per cent.).

Tetracetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as a brown microcrystalline powder, m.p. above 250°. (Found: N, 6.88. $C_{22}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires N 6.9 per cent.).

Dibromo derivative prepared by adding bromine water to a solution of the base in dilute hydrochloric acid crystallised from alcohol as a brown microcrystalline powder, m.p. above 250°. (Found: Br, 41.6. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 41.8 per cent.).

o-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol* was prepared in a manner analogous to that of *m*-dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol. It recrystallised from alcohol as a violet powder, m.p. above 250°. It dyes silk to a bluish violet shade from an acetic acid bath. (Found: N, 10.3. $C_{34}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires N, 10.1 per cent.).

o-*Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol sulphonic acid*.—It was prepared similarly as dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo-β-naphthol sulphonic acid (2:6) but starting from *o*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine. It is a brownish red powder dissolving in water to a red solution from which it dyes cotton and silk to a red shade. (Found: N, 7.82. $C_{34}H_{24}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N 7.7 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazo- β -naphthylamine, prepared from *o*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine (1.5 g.) and β -naphthylamine (2.2 g.) in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol as a red microcrystalline powder, m.p. above 250°. It dissolves in glacial acetic acid to a reddish orange solution. It dyes silk a reddish orange shade from an acetic acid bath. (Found: N, 16.26. $C_{30}H_{32}O_2N_6$ requires N, 16.5 per cent.).

o-Dihydroxymethylbenzidinebisazodimethylaniline was prepared from tetrazotised *o*-dihydroxymethylbenzidine by coupling with an ice-cold solution of dimethylaniline and subsequent treatment with alkali. The compound was purified from alcohol as a dark coloured powder, m.p. above 250°. It dyes silk to a violet shade from an acid bath. (Found: N, 14.26. $C_{34}H_{28}N_6O_2$ requires N, 14.4 per cent.).

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